
**ON THE DIVERSITY OF MOTIVATIONAL-NOMINATIVE ATTRIBUTES
IN NAMING MEDICINAL PLANTS IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK
LANGUAGES**

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Abstract: In this article, the study investigates how medical plant names in Russian and Uzbek languages are motivated and named. It examines motivation synchronically and diachronically, revealing associations with cultural values and plant properties. This comparative approach sheds light on the linguistic and cultural aspects of medicinal plant naming.

Keywords: motivation, naming, motivational features, onomasiological approach, medicinal plants, phytonyms, russian and uzbek languages.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of comparative motivology can be traced back to its foundation on descriptive motivology concepts like "motivational meaning," "motivating part," "motif," "motivator," "motifeme," and others. The emergence of scientific works on comparative motifology further indicates the development of this field.⁶⁴

As it is known, in the comparative-motivological plan the research is carried out on the basis of word motivation, because without it such an analysis has no linguistic sense. The concept of word motivation is interpreted as "a structural-semantic property of a word, which allows us to distinguish the rationality of the connection between the meaning and the sound meaning of the word on the basis of its lexical and structural correlation"⁶⁵.

On the other hand, motivation is the act of reflecting the feature of an object from the past in its naming by means of language and includes:

- 1) motivation of naming and the study of the regularities of the objective world (ontological property of motivation);
- 2) motivation of naming and the internal form of the word (semantic aspect);
- 3) motivation and its systemic relations in the lexicon;

^{1]} Bulakh E.A. Motivational bases of everyday names of plants (on the material of English, German and French languages). - Pyatigorsk, 2001. - C.16.

^{65]} Grigorieva E.A., Petrova O.A.. To the question of semantics of folk names of plants in differently structured languages (on the material of Russian and English phytonyms) // Vestnik ChSU, 2015.-№2.

4) motivation and the process of communication (functional aspect).⁶⁶.

Motivation includes the signified and signifier, on the one hand, and the immanent regularities of language development, on the other.

It is worth noting that motivation is considered as a state in synchronicity, while motivation is revealed in diachrony. In other words, in order to establish the motivation of a word, one has to turn to the etymological origins of words. In some cases, "... it is very difficult to set a limit to which one can reach when trying to find the origins of motivation, since the iconic nature of language is constantly resisting such motivation, and the language sign itself, which may have once had a clear source of motivation, tends to get rid of it"⁶⁷. . Besides, when it comes to the etymology of borrowed words, we should take into account that their motivation remains within the source language. Therefore, in the course of the motivological analysis of words it is necessary, first of all, to consider the origin, historical development, modification, possible reinterpretation of the name and, if possible, to establish the motive of the name. To achieve this goal, special approaches to the study of linguistic units in a comparative-comparative way have been developed in motif analysis. As A.D. Zhakupov notes, three approaches are traditionally distinguished in the study of word motivation: word formation, semasiological and onomasiological.⁶⁸

1. Motivation in the word-formation approach is considered as a property of a derived word, as the conditionality of its meaning by the meaning of another word from which it is formed.

2. The semasiological approach considers word motivation as a lexicological phenomenon (along with synonymy, antonymy, word variation, etc.), where the analysis of a motivated word is carried out with the involvement of the lexical-semantic level of the language and the word is studied from the point of view of its semantic structure, properties, systemic relations.

3. The main task of the onomasiological approach is to reveal the principles of subject nomination, where the motivated is considered as the result of creating the form of naming an object on the basis of its feature that formed the basis of naming. "...The methodological basis of this kind of research consists of: 1) the theory of linguistic nomination, oriented towards revealing the principles, ways and means of nominative technique; 2) cognitive studies, aimed at describing conceptual structures and conceptual categories reflected in those or other linguistic units, as well as at

⁶⁶] Grigorieva E.A., Petrova O.A.. To the question of semantics of folk names of plants in differently structured languages (on the material of Russian and English phytonyms) // Vestnik of the Czech State University, 2015.-#2.

⁴]Zhakupov A.D. Parameters of comparative-motivological research of Slavic and Turkic languages/ Vesnik TomGU. 2008.-C.15-19.

⁶⁸] Omasheva J.M. Comparative methodology: theory and methods. Vestnik Karaganda State University. - Karaganda, 2011.

revealing the main channels of obtaining information about the extra-linguistic world and ways of presenting knowledge about it. The research attention of linguists is also focused on the involvement of a wide range of languages in order to identify specific features of motivational processes".

That is why we have chosen onomasiological approach in cognitive terms to study phytonyms in English, Russian and Uzbek languages. This makes it possible to understand and explain the stages of cognitive activity and occurs in the process of plant nomination, taking place in the consciousness of speakers of different languages. According to N.I. Panasenko, this activity takes place in the following four stages:

1) initial information - knowledge about where plants can be found, the time of their flowering, which of them can be used and how effective their use is;

2) processing the information obtained - comparing the plant to find similarities in shape, color, or other external features with other plants or objects;

3) involvement of the cultural background, which belongs to the social sphere of human existence rather than to the biological one;

4) final evaluation of useful properties - efficiency of use, etc. This last stage includes plants from a particular class: medicinal, poisonous, edible, used as raw materials, or other. If the association with a plant becomes more and more complex and the plant itself is compared to an object of cultural value, the human cognitive experience goes beyond sensory perception and includes the evaluation of factors leading to the formation of specific cultural concepts. During the processing of information about a new motivational attribute, the individual tends to draw on his or her background knowledge.⁶⁹

It is necessary to state that the attributes underlying the nomination of phytonyms are the main elements of analysis in the study of YACM of the languages under consideration. According to V.V. Kopocheva, "a feature is the presence or absence of any qualities, properties". An extra-linguistic feature of an object, fixed in a word and becoming the basis of nomination, is called a motivational feature. In principle, any property, quality of a reality can become a feature of nomination, form the basis of a name (name, appellation, nominative unit), the number of these properties and qualities is infinite"⁷⁰. N.D. Golev defines a motivational feature as one of the objective features of the reality itself, distinguished as a "representative" of

⁶⁹] Panasenko N.I. Contrastive analysis of metaphor in phytonymic lexicon // Nova philologiya.-Zaporizhzhya: ZNU, 2009. - № 36.-C. 129-136.

⁷⁰] Kopocheva V.V.. Correlation of natural and artificial nomination (on the material of plant names): Autoref: diss. ... Cand.philol. nauk. -Tomsk, 1985. -17 c

the totality of its features, capable of characterizing the given object in a number of its homogeneous ones most vividly⁷¹.

METHODS

In our opinion, the motivational feature (hereinafter referred to as MP) represents the whole range of anthropocentric associations based on the properties of the plant and objects or concepts of cultural value for a certain nation.

It should be noted that MFs of phytonyms were the objects of the works of such researchers as V.V. Kopacheva, O.P. Ryabko, T.D. Baryshnikova, E.L. Bulakhi, etc. In these cases, the study did not require a large amount of information (only dictionaries were used), as it was based on purely linguistic material. We would like to note that the information extracted from dictionaries is insufficient to determine the motive of nomination.

Firstly, in this case the definitions given characterize the plant from the botanical point of view, and this information is not always significant for determining the motivational feature.

Secondly, dictionaries contain mainly scientific names, so, for example, biological and botanical dictionaries give binary names consisting of species epithet and genus name. But in living colloquial vocabulary only generic names are used, as a rule.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Besides, some works offer too complicated and detailed classification of MFs for analyzing composite and word-combination phytonyms.

In our opinion, it is not quite practical to apply such a detailed classification for determining MF phytonyms in a comparative aspect, since not all languages have phytonyms with such diversity. It is also inappropriate to divide them into subgroups from the point of view of the transparency of the nominator's motivation or attitude. Such a detailed classification of MFs brings to the background the most important goal of comparative research determining the peculiar and common features of the languages under consideration. Therefore, it is more suitable for analyzing phytonyms on the material of one language.

Motivational features of plant names in English, Russian and Uzbek languages are quite diverse. This was demonstrated by the work with dictionaries (biological, botanical, etymological) and the analysis of scientific works on lexicology (thematic collections of articles, author's works devoted to the lexicon of individual languages). Based on the collected material, a scheme for identifying the motif and MF of phytonyms in each of the languages under consideration was formed: phytonyms

^{71]} Golev N.D. On the principle of nomination and the method of their study // Proceedings of the scientific conference devoted to the 50th anniversary of education. - Vp.5. Linguistics. Theoretical issues of the Russian language and its govoras. - Tomsk, 1972. -C. 94-99.

were selected from sources; their scientific and literal translation from English or Uzbek into Russian was determined; history and origin were established; historical and cultural information was studied; botanical description and practical application were reviewed. Thus, on the basis of numerous sources, a new (author's) interpretation of the motif of plant nomination in the languages under consideration is given.

Many researchers who analyzed MF phytonyms considered only composite and collocational phytonyms, because they believed that due to the opaque motivation it is not possible to identify their motivational features. In our opinion, it is more correct to consider this or that type of phytonyms on the basis of morphological properties of the languages under study. Thus, for example, in English and Uzbek, a significant part of motivated phytonyms are complex-structured, i.e. composite and word-combinations phytonyms. Therefore, analyzing the motivation in phytonyms of these languages, we mainly consider complex-structured (composite and collocational) phytonyms. In Russian, a significant part of motivated phytonyms is not complex-structured phytonyms, but simple derivatives, hence, it is more appropriate to analyze MFs of these phytonyms on a par with other types. At the same time, it should be emphasized that the internal form of phytonyms is no less important than the external form, as it is the analysis of the internal form of phytonyms that gives an opportunity to better understand the depth of the association underlying the motif. For this reason, all complex-structured phytonyms are divided into endocentric and exocentric formations for correct motif analysis. On this basis, in this section we analyzed about 107 Russian and 84 Uzbek phytonyms according to the scheme given in the table.

In the course of the study, we have developed our own version of the classification of MFs of commonly used phytonyms, which aims mainly to reflect the similarities, differences and peculiarities of English, Russian and Uzbek plant names.

A detailed analysis of phytonyms in Russian and Uzbek for each MF is presented below.

	Motivational features	Russian phytonyms	Uzbek phytonyms
1.	Shape	22 (30%)	12 (19 %)
2.	Locative	10 (13,5 %)	11 (17,5 %)
3.	Functional application	8 (10,8%)	6 (9,5 %)
4.	Coloration	9 (12,2%)	8 (12,7 %)
5.	Texture	5 (6,8 %)	4 (6,4 %)
6.	Time	3 (4 %)	1 (1,6 %)
7.	Taste	4 (5,4%)	2 (3,2 %)
8.	Sound	1 (1,4 %)	2 (3,2 %)

9.	Odor	6 (8,1 %)	9 (14,3)
10.	Way of growing	4 (5,4 %)	3 (5%)
11.	Quantities	2 (2,7%)	5 (8 %)

This MF is one of the oldest and most important features underlying the nomination of phytonyms. Since ancient times, man has lived in close connection with the world of plants. To distinguish and designate plants, it was necessary to name them. On this basis, the comparison of some forms of plants with those forms that exist in other subject areas of reality began. In this case, the association had an anthropocentric character, i.e. the properties of plants that are important primarily for humans were emphasized. Therefore, often those objects or phenomena that had a certain value in the culture of native speakers were chosen for naming plants.

In phytonyms formed on the basis of the MF "Form", there is often an association with somatisms (human or animal), insects, birds, artifacts of everyday life, natural phenomena, abstract notions, the plant world, etc. The phytonyms are often used to name plants.

Let us give examples of definitions of some names with the motivational feature "form" in each of the languages under consideration. In Russian, names with the motivational feature "form" are represented by simple derivatives, as well as endocentric and exocentric formations:

bell - the flowers of the plant look like bells;

star - MF indicates a star-shaped form (usually leaves, flowers);

cuff - the toothed shape of the leaves resembles the ruffle of a lace cuff;

rattlesnake - flowers are gathered in spike-like clusters at the top of the stem, resembling a rattlesnake.

In Uzbek, the representativeness ratio between simple derivatives and complex-structured phytonyms, as in English, is explained by the fact that in many cases root and simple derivative phytonyms are indigenous and have lost their motivation, but complex-structured phytonyms are usually characterized by clear and transparent motivation:

endocentric formations:

gulkaram (lit. "cauliflower") - cauliflower, the shape of the plant is associated with the flower;

azhdargul (lit. "dragon's flower") - lion's pharynx, the open flowers of the plant resemble the mouth of a dragon, this is easily the basis of the name;

exocentric formations:

quzikorin (lit. "lamb's belly") - the true morel, the shriveled texture of the mushroom is associated with the inside of a lamb's abdomen (meaning a lamb carcass).

CONCLUSION

The analysis shows that although the MF "form" is productive in all the languages under consideration, each language has its own peculiar types of associations. In Russian, the MF "form" is mainly manifested in derivative phytonyms based on simple direct associations. Sometimes the name of the object itself, associated with the form of a plant, turns into the name of the plant and becomes a phytonym (bell, zvezdochka, cuff, rattle, marigolds). The association of plant shape with animal body parts is more characteristic of the Uzbek language. Such association is found in both Russian and Uzbek, so it can be considered as a similar property of the compared and contrasted languages.

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